

Original Article

Conditioning Climate Resilience with International Collaboration: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Dawn's Special Report

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Abstract

Climate change is a dominantly debated and discussed topic in media, policy and policy discourses. Nations across the globe are busy in developing measures to cope with climate related challenges, mitigation, adaptation and resilience. International organizations have come up with several policy agendas, proposals, standards and regulations to be implemented. Media is playing its role in disseminating these discussions to facilitate the implementation in local contexts and actively constructing discourses to garner policy support from public and policymakers. This article analyses discourses of Dawn's Special Report to reveal how international collaboration in climate resilience is constructed, legitimized and necessitated. CDA reveals that dominant discourses of necessity, moral imperative, justice, economic rationality, strategic need, domestic institutional sloth and climate governance are constructed, all legitimizing the calls for international collaboration in order to seek access to global climate finance. The discourses are coherent and aligned to the global discourse of urgent coordination and demands of socio-political transformation. International collaboration is presented as an essential element for climate resilience from global perspective. A balanced perspective needs countering the arguments and transcending the dominant discourses in order to explore other actionable alternatives.

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Introduction

Climate Change and Climate Resilience have gained immense degree of attention all over the world (Nüchter et al., 2021). Global and national media is informing about the ongoing situation of climate change (Vu et al., 2019; Song et al., 2021) and updating the masses about the recent developments at the national and international level (McAllister et al., 2024). Climate change is framed as a planetary threat (Cuk et al., 2021). Climate resilience and adaptation to climate change have become urgent political concerns (Scoville-Simonds et al., 2019). Media, being a crucial tool of the state system, is playing its role of mediation between the policymakers and the audience. Pakistan's eminent English newspaper, Dawn, is regularly presenting analysis, briefs and reports on climate change. Recently, it published a special report titled "Climate Change & Climate Resilience" on February 6, 2025. This Report consists of 12 detailed articles written by renowned analysts, journalists, policymakers and other professionals.

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International cooperation and collaboration for climate resilience are emphasized by the international institutions and organizations (Lehmann, 2024). This insistence on collaboration can be problematized from multiple aspects from moral to pragmatic. Climate resilience involves efforts in coping with climate-related calamities. Climate resilience depends on the abilities, capacities and resources of the local populations and communities. Local populations are facing different levels and forms of climate change. Different populations have different perceptions about causes and consequences of climate change. All these factors seem to negate the standardization of climate change perceptions and resilience to it. International institutions may have adopted a discourse of climate change and a standard view of resilience to be promoted rather than imposed and implemented across the nations but this discursive dominance may be challenged by local epistemic and ethical frameworks. A crucial matter is not to challenge or accept the standard notions of climate change and resilience, the actual issue of concern is to have a real solution to the risks of climate change, the solutions that are beneficial to others in the near as well as distant future. The benevolence of internationally proposed solutions and propagated through commercial media become suspicious because these very institutions and media houses have enthusiastically promoted and propagated the developmental policies that have led to the current climate crisis (Perry, 2021). Climate resilience is not free from problematic development frameworks as it is argued that successfully combating it can help achieve the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (Nerini et al., 2019). In this sense, it becomes a legitimate research problem to analyze the role of media in collaboration with international organizations that tend to frame, analyze and solve problems from their own developmental and economic perspectives.

Research Questions

In this background and context, this paper investigates how Dawn's Special Report on "Climate Change & Climate Resilience" constructs and frames climate resilience in relation to international collaboration, and discusses the implications of this discursive construction. This objective is achieved through the following research questions:

1. How Dawn's Special Report constructs discourses of international collaboration for climate resilience in Pakistan?
2. What discursive strategies and dominant discourses are employed to necessitate, emphasize and legitimize international collaboration regarding climate resilience in Pakistan?
3. What assumptions and arguments support these discourses, and what implications can be drawn from this discursive reasoning?

Literature Review

Academic researchers have argued for comprehensive international collaboration in climate change and resilience. International cooperation in climate change started in 2015 and has produced multiple structures of governance (Chan et al., 2018). Clare B. Gaffey argued that climate change effects will be managed and monitored effectively if international collaboration and participation is strengthened (Gaffey et al., 2024). This international cooperation in climate resilience is effused with targeted transformations in norms and behaviors to get individual and collective support (Carattini et al., 2019). This implies that new standards and parameters will enforce a new normal replacing current practices through social engineering. It is also argued that policies should be decentralized and confidence building efforts should be initiated for a "deeper" international cooperation (Keohane & Victor, 2016). Emphasis on international collaboration is advocated on the ground that it has proven advantageous in monitoring climate change and better understanding of it (Peterson & Manton, 2008). Not only climate monitoring and collaboration, but collaborative "governance" of climate change is a tool for governments and communities for adaptation to climate change (Harmawan et al., 2024). In its governance anchoring, collaboration is primarily a political

globalization (Chen et al., 2020). Moreover, collaboration is dominated by positivist approach whereby quantifiable objectives are valued more (De Pinto et al., 2017). Scientific research collaboration in climate change is negatively effective reference balance (Qiu et al., 2024) because of imbalance in research resources among different nations. This imbalance in knowledge production is also caused by the fact that now climate change collaboration is not focused on understanding but on policymaking and technological innovation (Fu & Waltman, 2021).

Media constructs climate change discourse validating scientific information, mentioning possible risks, overviewing political measures and supporting resilience efforts (Broadbent et al., 2016). In political framing of climate change, the media frames the issue from social dimension highlighting awareness, vulnerability, mitigation and causes (Hase et al., 2021). This issue is so dominated on media that journalists have become curators widening the sphere of stakeholders to it (Schäfer & Painter, 2020). Overall, media reporting and discursive constructions of mitigation and resilience to climate change are positive and supportive (Bolsen & Shapiro, 2017). Media coverage of climate change is influenced by several factors including regional contexts and national political systems (Barkemeyer et al., 2017; Vu et al., 2019), level of development (Hase et al., 2021) and ideological influences (Bolsen & Shapiro, 2017; Eikelboom et al., 2024).

Methodology

Dawn's Special Report "Climate Change & Climate Resilience" dated February 6, 2025 was purposively selected for analysis. Dawn is a prestigious English newspaper in Pakistan that is popular among elites, policymakers and educated groups. It has established "Breathe Pakistan" media initiative to create awareness and advocate climate change issues, bringing experts and private & public institutions at one platform to explore solutions for climate change¹. For this purpose, its recent Special Report was selected for analysis. This Report consists of 12 articles authored by diverse individual experts. This Report was downloaded in PDF from Dawn's website². There are 28 pages of this Report, out of which exactly half, 14 pages, are filled up with advertisements. The text of the articles is packed into about 28000 words. All articles are written in English with author names. All the articles of the Report are analyzed through the critical discourse analysis framework and analytical tools provided by Fairclough (2003) and Wodak (Wodak & Meyer, 2009). Construction and representation of social actions of climate resilience and international collaboration/cooperation were explored along with intertextuality, modality and evaluation. Argumentative discourse analysis was conducted guided by Fairclough's (2017) Dialectical Reasoning.

Findings and Discussion

Discursive constructions

Dawn's Special Report constructs the discourses of "necessity", "morality", "justice", "expertise" and "flow of global resources" for international collaboration. It constructs that international collaboration is inevitable, not merely as a policy option but as a survival imperative. The opening sentence of the first article makes a declaration that "*Climate Justice is a global and domestic imperative*". It makes an active construction for the responses to climate change. Climate finance, international treaties and summits are constructed as events that are reactively developing and implementing response mechanisms to mitigate the risks of climate change and actively consolidating frameworks for future actions:

"Pakistan faces a serious climate finance gap, requiring an estimated \$348 billion for climate action by 2030, while currently accessing less than \$1 billion annually in international climate finance." (Integrate or Fail)

This discursive construction makes international collaboration indispensable for resilience and adaptation measures in Pakistan. The Report constructs overdetermination on global collaboration.

¹ Official description of Breathe Pakistan as provided on <https://www.dawn.com/breathepakistan/> (accessed on February 22, 2025).

²https://drive.usercontent.google.com/download?id=1pAQAcdAc5oFTzVWvRd_nZY1FqC7usQ&export=download&authuser=0

Greenhouse gas emissions are not same for all regions so “*reparative justice*” that is advocated in judicial approach tend to oversimplify complexity of global interdependencies that are made justifications for international collaboration. Quantification of legal instruments (*Loss and Damage Fund*), commitments (funding and contributions) serve as simplification of complex global dynamics to propose practical measures.

In terms of genre, the Report mixes policy actions with rhetoric of activism. International collaboration is presented in technical jargon (*carbon markets, ecosystems and carbon credits*) and as an “*moral imperative*” as well. This mixed genre legitimizes the urgent need for global collaboration on pragmatic grounds and also frames it as an ethical duty (*climate debt*) for the North to help the South. The Report situates its discursive constructions within the dominant international collaboration genre through provoking COP, the Kyoto Protocol, the Paris Agreement and UNFCCC. This contextualization of collaboration calls within institutional language tends to reinforce authorial authority and credibility on the one hand, and frames this collaboration as legitimate, normative and moral on the other hand.

The imperative for international collaboration for climate resilience is also constructed in terms of conflict and difference. The Report constructs this conflict by arguing that the North is the primary emitter and responsible for climate change to which developing countries are now vulnerable. Developing nations with negligible emission contributions are suffering more from the impacts of climate change; therefore, the Reports constructs moral and political imperatives for the primary emitters to finance and collaborate in climate resilience:

“Recognizing its significance, the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA) officially recognized the Living Indus Programme as a World Restoration Flagship in February 2024. This prestigious recognition places Pakistan at the global forefront of environmental restoration, signalling the nation’s leadership in the fight against climate change and its commitment to achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).” (The Indus Basin: A Model for Global Action)

Climate governance is also advocated in its constructions, arguing for balancing and redistribution of resources. Apart from the conflict of responsibility, there is another discourse contrasting slow and fragmented global action with the urgent need of coordination. Criticism on existing global efforts is employed to legitimize the radical call for international collaboration in resilience and adaptation to climate change. Credibility and authority are also deliberately constructed by selecting narratives from the judiciary, experts and international organizations. This selection of expert voices creates a discursive environment in which international collaboration for climate resilience becomes self-evident while dissent voices are excluded from the discourse.

The Report constructs collaboration imperative through some discursive assumptions. It is assumed that collaboration is a moral obligation, not an option. It assumes that “climate justice” and “*reparative justice*” are truly based on just principles as if inclusively agreed upon by all nations. The ironic assumption is that the primary emitters who are main culprits of the climate crisis have now decided to do justice and are ready to pay for their actions. This gives a sense of moral superiority to those who are culprits. Furthermore, this assumption, with underlying the discourses of climate justice and calls for collaboration, marginalizes the potential of developing nations for constructive actions. The Report’s calls for Pakistan’s integration in climate governance presume that international collaboration in climate resilience will produce and provide the required resources, techniques and technologies to escape from the climate crisis. The Report constructs domestic challenges (“*mounting debt*” and the need for alignment with “*donor priorities*”) as legitimation ground that, only through global integration and collaboration Pakistan, can overcome its climate related problems. The need imperative is framed as:

“For Pakistan and other Global South countries, the key lies in adopting a dual approach: holding the Global North accountable while building self-reliance through innovative financing and resilience-building strategies. A collective, well-coordinated effort across vulnerable nations can amplify their voice and secure a fairer share of climate financing to address their pressing adaptation and loss-and-damage needs.” (Climate Justice is Inevitable)

It is existentially imperative for Pakistan and ethical duty of the country to seek collaboration. Parallel assumption is that such provisions will necessarily be beneficial for local communities, free of cost and free from potential risks. This optimistic discourse is reasonably constructed within the post-colonial exploitation that is occurring in the name of green capitalism. It is evident from this optimism that international collaboration is legitimized with the hope of tangible resources flowing to Pakistan. But a contradiction appears in the discursive construction of climate finance: *“No Pakistani government institution presently holds direct access accreditation with the relevant global funds”*. The contradiction is that global collaboration is not only a matter of climate justice but also of finance, hence, injustice is bare in global labyrinth of climate financing from where Pakistan is expecting more despite with low carbon footprint.

As is clear from imperative discourse, the linguistic mode adopted for international collaboration is dominantly assertive making the collaboration a binding duty. The Report constructs international organizations as actors and authorities while local governments are constructed as passive recipients or technical and financial support and always entangled in national constraints. The discourse expresses strong epistemic and deontic modality by employing verbs “need to”, “shall” and “must”. This reveals high level of trust in the certainty of scientific information on climate change provided by the international organizations:

“With fiscal constraints and rising debt levels, Pakistan cannot afford to rely solely on public funds to finance its climate response. Private sector engagement is critical to mobilizing large-scale investment in climate resilience and low-carbon development...Beyond funding, private sector participation brings technological innovation, efficiency, and expertise, fostering solutions that are both economically viable and sustainable.” (Cracking the Code of Climate Finance).

This is a form of epistemic sovereignty and epistemic colonization in which victim is urgently seeking collaboration with its victimizer because of knowledge differential, a knowledge produced and provided by the latter. This epistemic modality constructs international collaboration not only as a moral imperative but as an existential requirement. The capabilities of the developed countries are deemed essential in climate resilience – as if resilience is impossible without their support.

Discursive strategies and dominant discourses

The Report employs a number of discursive strategies in order to legitimize, emphasize and necessitate international collaboration for climate resilience. The necessity and urgency for international interventions is amplified by the strategic use of hyperbolic language emphasizing crisis. The crisis discourse is highlighted through catastrophic scenario such as *“serial instability”* and *“a 40pc surge in water demand”*. These projections are coupled with definite economic figures *“gap of billions”* in climate finance. Pakistan’s vulnerability is highlighted to seek global financial resources:

“Despite contributing less than 1pc to global GHG emissions, Pakistan remains one of the most climate-vulnerable nations...” (Translating Policies into Climate Resilience).

“Pakistan’s relationship with the climate crisis is defined by extreme vulnerability.” (From Policy to Actions: the 2047 Alternative)

These emotive and empirical strategies are grounded in economic rationality. The emotive strategy legitimizes international collaboration and the economic strategy rationalizes global flows of climate finance for catastrophic situation in Pakistan. The discourses of justice are ideologically embedded.

“Climate justice demands that those primarily responsible for climate change, namely the global North, pay off their ‘ecological debt’.” (Climate Justice is Inevitable).

Climate finance is seen as a new opportunity of international aid, implying domestic weaknesses and inertia as advantage, making Pakistan an eligible recipient:

“Climate finance is actually our lifeline that can help us strengthen our infrastructure, agriculture, water management, health, displacement and migration, economic inequality, and disaster resilience. It must be mobilised on an unprecedented scale and be accessible in a timely manner to those who need it the most.” (Climate Justice is Inevitable).

International collaboration and intervention are invoked through equity principles so that these actions get a moral frame through assertions of *“climate justice is inevitable”* for making climate finance necessary for the compensation of *“communities for harm caused by environmental degradation”*. Contrary to the economic discourse, emphasis on moral economy tends to delegitimize market logic but simultaneously invoke the institutions that follow market dynamics. This moral discourse transforms *“climate debt”* into *“ethical debt”* implying that the emitters who immorally contributed to climate crisis would now respond to moral invocations. The Report delegitimizes national institutional setups through the use of direct quotations highlighting bureaucratic bottlenecks. This discursive strategy also legitimizes international resources and expertise. The assumption is that Pakistan’s *“institutional sloth”* is an indication of flawed local governance and only international partners and governing standards can help in climate resilience. Furthermore, this discourse necessitates alignment of national policies and laws with international climate governance. Already, alignment is appreciated and Pakistan is constructed as a leader in climate change actions, ignoring previously lamented institutional incapacities:

“The Government of Pakistan has established itself as an important voice in global climate diplomacy, having successfully advocated for the creation of a global climate ‘Loss and Damage Fund’ at the COP27 Climate Conference two years ago.” (A ‘Living Indus’)

Assumptions and implications

The Report’s discursive reasoning is established on multiple related assumptions and arguments. Arguments for vulnerability/dependency, moral imperative, policy and sovereignty, climate justice, climate finance and technical support are based on assumptions. Pakistan is assumed to be vulnerable to climate calamities. This vulnerability is presented in terms of environmental challenges, demographic situations and economic constraints. Pakistan’s dependency is assumed inevitable and sufficient evidence for international collaboration. Deficits of *“innovation capacity”* and *“renewable energy investment”* may be limitations but the report argues that these are standard qualifications to beg for financial assistance. Moral arguments are made on the assumption that developed nations will forget their technological might and will become morally corrective to pay for their past deeds of contributing to environmental degradation. It is also assumed that global climate finance is intrinsically beneficial for Pakistan. Collectively, the arguments of the Report reinforce dependency narrative. Foreign intervention is legitimized as permanent need. These arguments for international collaboration marginalize local knowledge systems, local agency and national sovereignty and autonomy.

Argument analysis

The Report is rich in arguments that are based on multiple assumptions with diverse implications. Central arguments of the Report are analyzed to complement the discursive analysis. Discourse of international collaboration is presented in several arguments. The argument is that international collaboration and assistance is *necessary for bridging the existence gap in resources* and Pakistan will be able to implement global mitigation and adaptation regulations. This argument is based on the assumption that Pakistan doesn't have the capacity, institutions and resources to address climate change. This argument may perpetuate dependence on global organizations and domestic innovations may remain persistent so that financial resource supply may continue. Another argument is that *climate finance is a form of reparative justice*, not a charity. This argument is based on the assumption that developed countries are responsible for climate crisis and are obliged to assist the vulnerable ones. Irrespective of advocacy effectiveness, this argument places responsibility and blame for climate crisis solely on technologically advanced countries but historically, the developmental aspirations of all countries may lead to equality of blame. An argument is that collaboration and cooperation is necessary because it is a transborder issue. This argument is based on the assumption that international collaboration is only possible way to address climate change challenges and this collaboration will necessarily involve coordinate efforts, technology transfer and knowledge sharing. This argument overlooks diverse interests and priorities of international stakeholders, interest groups and actors.

Delving into detailed reasoning analysis, the reasoning process of arguments can also be checked for their validity. Argument for having a share in climate finance is structured on two premises: Pakistan faces severe climate finance gap (of \$347 billion) and that institutional barriers are limiting Pakistan's ability to access international climate finance. It is inferred from these premises that reforms in financial strategies are needed as the barriers are acting as constraints in resource mobilization. The conclusion is that Pakistan must diversify financing sources to have direct access to international climate finance. This argument is based on quantitative evidence. This argument can be criticized that heavy reliance on international finance can create dependency thereby undermining local governance of national climate policies. Integration with global standards and policies may end up in alien policies that are not comprehensively aligned with local realities. First difficult step is to secure international finance but even harder step is to fairly and effectively distribute this finance – and this seems highly suspicious given the institutional inefficiencies and corruption in Pakistan. Since already received development funds are not efficiently distributed, it cannot be guaranteed that climate funds will be effectively utilized towards real objectives.

The second major argument is that institutional alignment and linkage with international institutions is required to gain international support and to realize adaptation and mitigation strategies. This is inferred from two premises. The first one is that international institutions and bodies have established mechanisms that offer knowledge sharing, technical innovation and direct access to climate finance. The Second premise is that Pakistan is actively participating in global initiatives and is sincerely committed to climate governance. This argument is structured in pragmatic and normative reasoning, implying that international collaboration is not optional. This argument can be countered by concerns about sovereignty and power dynamics. Engagement in global arena will lead to compromise on national sovereignty, consequent in a situation in which global policies are dominant and implemented but are alien to local contexts. Secondly, existing imbalanced power relations and economic power dynamics penetrate in climate governance frameworks that marginalize developing nations, hence, leading to the implementation of potentially counterproductive resilience policies.

Third major argument is that while seeking international collaboration domestic and local needs must be considered in resilience policies. This is inferred from the support imperative and unique domestic context. The argument is based on the premises that Pakistan is disproportionately affected by climate crisis but at the same time dependence on calibration with international organizations is resulting in declined policy autonomy. This reasoning is based on strategic evaluation of asymmetric power dynamics in climate governance and

consideration of reformed policy and cooperation model. This reasoning argues that international collaboration is complementary in climate resilience, not policy dictation. This reasoning oversimplifies the complex task of seeking a balance between national sovereignty and international support. Assertion of domestically aligned policies may lead to limited access or flow of required climate finance and expertise. Secondly, as the discourses of this Report argue, domestic institutional capacities are limited and there is lack of technology and innovation that may create hurdles in implementation of domestic as well as global solutions. In this situation, the dilemma between the imperative of external support and demand of self-reliance prevails.

Conclusion

Dawn's Special Report calls for, legitimizes and necessitate international collaboration in climate resilience strategies. The Report presents multiple discourses through various discursive and logic constructions, from financial resources to transboundary alliances, to necessitate international collaboration to counter intricate challenges of climate change. Each argument and discourses are situated in the broader perspective that climate resilience in Pakistan is conditioned with domestic policy reforms and international alliance. CDA reveals that the texts report climate resilience and actively engages in discursive strategies and constructions interlinking climate crisis, climate injustice, moral obligation of primary emitters and ethical duty of vulnerable nations to support global climate mitigation measures. The Report combines institutional critique, ethical imperative and quantitative evidence to legitimize international collaboration as a remedial measure reflecting global institutional mainstream discourse. International collaboration is needed to seek financial resources and it is argued that Pakistan lacks such institutional and material resources. The arguments of the Report are coherent and based on evidence. Quantitative data as well as qualitative evaluations are provided to support the claims. Strategically, the Report argues for an enhanced but balanced collaboration. Climate challenges are linked with collaboration. However, the Report is not balanced in perspective. Counter-arguments highlighting potential risks of implementation issues, coordination challenges, sovereignty concerns and dependency are required to balance the perspective.

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